

CRR
JOURNAL
OF CARDIORESPIRATORY RESEARCH

ISSN 2181-0974
DOI 10.26739/2181-0974
Impact Factor SJIF 2022: 5.937

Journal of

**CARDIORESPIRATORY
RESEARCH**

Volume 4, Issue 3

2023

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Журнал кардиореспираторных исследований

JOURNAL OF CARDIORESPIRATORY RESEARCH

Главный редактор: Э.Н.ТАШКЕНБАЕВА

Учредитель:

Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет

Tadqiqot.uz

Ежеквартальный
научно-практический
журнал

ISSN: 2181-0974
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0974

N^o 3
2023

Главный редактор:

Ташкенбаева Элеонора Негматовна

доктор медицинских наук, заведующая кафедрой внутренних болезней №2 Самаркандского Государственного медицинского университета, председатель Ассоциации терапевтов Самаркандской области. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5705-4972>

Заместитель главного редактора:

Хайбулина Зарина Руслановна

доктор медицинских наук, руководитель отдела биохимии с группой микробиологии ГУ «РСНПМЦХ им. акад. В. Вахидова» <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9942-2910>

ЧЛЕНЫ РЕДАКЦИОННОЙ КОЛЛЕГИИ:

Аляви Анис Лютфуллаевич

академик АН РУз, доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Председатель Ассоциации Терапевтов Узбекистана, Советник директора Республиканского специализированного научно-практического центра терапии и медицинской реабилитации (Ташкент) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0933-4993>

Бокерия Лео Антонович

академик РАН, доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Президент научного центра сердечно-сосудистой хирургии им. А.Н. Бакулева (Москва), <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6180-2619>

Курбанов Равшанбек Давлетович

академик АН РУз, доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Советник директора Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра кардиологии (Ташкент), <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7309-2071>

Шкляев Алексей Евгеньевич

д.м.н., профессор, ректор Федерального государственного бюджетного образовательного учреждения высшего образования «Ижевская государственная медицинская академия» Министерства здравоохранения Российской Федерации

Michał Tendera

профессор кафедры кардиологии Верхнесилезского кардиологического центра, Силезский медицинский университет в Катовице, Польша (Польша) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0812-6113>

Покушалов Евгений Анатольевич

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заместитель генерального директора по науке и развитию сети клиник «Центр новых медицинских технологий» (ЦНМТ), (Новосибирск), <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-5167>

Зуфаров Миржамол Мирумарович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, руководитель отдела ГУ «РСНПМЦХ им. акад. В. Вахидова» <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4822-3193>

Акилов Хабибулла Атауллаевич

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Директор Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников (Ташкент)

Абдиева Гулнора Алиевна

PhD, ассистент кафедры внутренних болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6980-6278> (ответственный секретарь)

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5468-9403>

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худойбердиевич

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Самаркандского Государственного медицинского университета <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9309-3933>

Джан Ковак

Профессор, председатель Совета Европейского общества кардиологов по инсульту, руководитель специализированной кардиологии, заведующий отделением кардиологии, кардио- и торакальной хирургии, консультант-кардиолог, больница Гленфилд, Лестер (Великобритания)

Сергио Бернадини

Профессор клинической биохимии и клинической молекулярной биологии, главный врач отдела лабораторной медицины, больница Университета Тор Вергата (Рим, Италия)

Ливерко Ирина Владимировна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заместитель директора по науке Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра фтизиатрии и пульмонологии Республики Узбекистан (Ташкент) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0059-9183>

Цурко Владимир Викторович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Первого Московского государственного медицинского университета им. И.М. Сеченова (Москва) <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8040-3704>

Камилова Умида Кабировна

д.м.н., профессор, заместитель директора по научной работе Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра терапии и медицинской реабилитации (Ташкент) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1190-7391>

Тураев Феруз Фатхуллаевич

доктор медицинских наук, Директор Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра эндокринологии имени академика Ю.Г. Туракулова

Bosh muharrir:

Tashkenbayeva Eleonora Negmatovna

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti 2-sonli ichki kasalliklar kafedrasini mudiri,
Samarqand viloyati vrachlar uyushmasi raisi.
<https://orsid.org/0000-0001-5705-4972>*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Xaibulina Zarina Ruslanovna

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, "akad V. Vohidov nomidagi RIJM davlat institutining mikrobiologiya guruhi
bilan biokimyo kafedrasini mudiri" <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9942-2910>*

TAHRIRIYAT A'ZOLARI:

Alyavi Anis Lyutfullayevich

*O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasining akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
O'zbekiston Terapevtlar uyushmasi raisi, Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan ilmiy va amaliy tibbiy terapiya markazi va tibbiy reabilitatsiya direktori maslahatchisi (Toshkent), <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0933-4993>*

Bockeria Leo Antonovich

*Rossiya fanlar akademiyasining akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, A.N. Bakuleva nomidagi yurak-qon tomir jarrohligi ilmiy markazi prezidenti (Moskva)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6180-2619>*

Kurbanov Ravshanbek Davlatovich

*O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasining akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan kardiologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazining direktor maslahatchisi (Toshkent)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7309-2071>*

Shklyayev Aleksey Evgenievich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Rossiya Federatsiyasi Sog'liqni saqlash vazirligining "Izhevsk davlat tibbiyot akademiyasi" Federal davlat byudjeti oliy ta'lim muassasasi rektori

Mixal Tendera

*Katovitsadagi Sileziya Tibbiyot Universiteti, Yuqori Sileziya Kardiologiya Markazi kardiologiya kafedrasini professori (Polsha)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0812-6113>*

Pokushalov Evgeniy Anatolevich

tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, "Yangi tibbiy texnologiyalar markazi" (YTTM) klinik tarmog'ining ilmiy ishlar va rivojlanish bo'yicha bosh direktorining o'rinbosari (Novosibirsk) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-5167>

Zufarov Mirjamol Mirumarovich

tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, "akad V. Vohidov nomidagi RIJM davlat muassasasi" bo'limi boshlig'i" <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4822-3193>

Akilov Xabibulla Ataulayevich

tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini oshirish markazi direktori (Toshkent)

Abdiyeva Gulnora Aliyevna

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti 2-sonli ichki kasalliklar kafedrasini assistenti, PhD (mas'ul kotib)

Rizayev Jasur Alimjanovich

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti rektori
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5468-9403>*

Ziyadullayev Shuxrat Xudoyberdiyevich

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent, Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universitetining fan va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori (Samarqand)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9309-3933>*

Jan Kovak

Yevropa kardiologiya jamiyati insulti kengashi raisi, 2017 yildan buyon ixtisoslashtirilgan kardiologiya kafedrasini rahbari, kardiologiya, yurak va torakal jarrohlik kafedrasini mudiri, maslahatchi kardiolog Glenfild kasalxonasi, Lester (Buyuk Britaniya)

Sergio Bernardini

Klinik biokimyo va klinik molekulyar biologiya bo'yicha professor - Laboratoriya tibbiyoti bo'limi bosh shifokori – Tor Vergata universiteti kasalxonasi (Rim-Italiya)

Liverko Irina Vladimirovna

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan fiziologiya va pulmonologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazining ilmiy ishlar bo'yicha direktor o'rinbosari (Toshkent)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0059-9183>*

Surko Vladimir Viktorovich

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professori I.M. Sechenov nomidagi Birinchi Moskva Davlat tibbiyot universiteti (Moskva)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8040-3704>*

Kamilova Umida Kabirovna

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan terapiya va tibbiy reabilitatsiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi ilmiy ishlari bo'yicha direktor o'rinbosari (Toshkent)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1190-7391>*

Turayev Feruz Fatxullayevich

*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, akademik Y.X.To'raqulov nomidagi Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan endokrinologiya ilmiy amaliy tibbiyot markazi direktori
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1321-4732>*

Chief Editor:

Tashkenbaeva Eleonora Negmatovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the Department of Internal Diseases No. 2 of the Samarkand State Medical University, Chairman of the Association of Physicians of the Samarkand Region.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5705-4972>

Deputy Chief Editor:

Xaibulina Zarina Ruslanovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the Department of Biochemistry with the Microbiology Group of the State Institution "RSSC named after acad. V. Vakhidov", <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9942-2910>

MEMBERS OF THE EDITORIAL BOARD:

Alyavi Anis Lutfullaevich

Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Chairman of the Association of Physicians of Uzbekistan, Advisor to the Director of the Republican Specialized Scientific - Practical Center of Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation (Tashkent)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0933-4993>

Bockeria Leo Antonovich

Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, President of the Scientific Center for Cardiovascular Surgery named after A.N. Bakuleva (Moscow)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6180-2619>

Kurbanov Ravshanbek Davletovich

Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Advisor to the Director Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Cardiology, (Tashkent)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7309-2071>

Shklyayev Aleksey Evgenievich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Rector of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "Izhevsk State Medical Academy" of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation

Michal Tendera

Professor of the Department of Cardiology, Upper Silesian Cardiology Center, Silesian Medical University in Katowice, Poland (Poland)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0812-6113>

Pokushalov Evgeny Anatolyevich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Deputy Director General for Science and Development of the Clinic Network "Center for New Medical Technologies" (CNMT), (Novosibirsk)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-5167>

Akilov Xabibulla Ataulloevich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Center for the development of professional qualifications of medical workers (Tashkent)

Abdieva Gulnora Alievna

PhD, assistant of the Department of Internal Diseases No. 2 of the Samarkand State Medical University
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6980-6278>
(Executive Secretary)

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5468-9403>

Ziyadullaev Shuhrat Khudoyberdievich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor, Vice-Rector for Science and Innovation of the Samarkand State Medical University (Samarkand)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9309-3933>

Jan Kovac

Professor Chairman, European Society of Cardiology Council for Stroke, Lead of Specialised Cardiology, Head of Cardiology, Cardiac and Thoracic Surgery, Consultant Cardiologist, Glenfield Hospital, Leicester (United Kingdom)

Sergio Bernardini

Full Professor in Clinical Biochemistry and Clinical Molecular Biology -Head Physician of the Laboratory Medicine Unit- University of Tor Vergata Hospital (Rome-Italy)

Liverko Irina Vladimirovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Deputy Director for Science of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Phthiology and Pulmonology of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Tashkent)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0059-9183>

Zufarov Mirjamol Mirumarovich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of the State Institution "RSNPMTSH named after acad. V. Vakhidov"
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4822-3193>

Tsurko Vladimir Viktorovich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, professor Of Moscow State Medical University by name I.M. Sechenov (Moscow)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8040-3704>

Kamilova Umida Kabirovna

Doctor of Medicine, professor, deputy director of Scientific unit of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center for therapy and medical rehabilitation (Tashkent)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1190-7391>

Turaev Feruz Fatxullaevich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Director of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology named after Academician Yu.G. Turakulova

Алимов Дониёр Анварович
доктор медицинских наук, директор
Республиканского научного центра
экстренной медицинской помощи

Янгиев Бахтиёр Ахмедович
кандидат медицинских наук,
директор Самаркандского филиала
Республиканского научного центра
экстренной медицинской помощи

Абдуллаев Акбар Хатамович
доктор медицинских наук, главный
научный сотрудник Республиканского
специализированного научно-
практического центра медицинской
терапии и реабилитации
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1766-4458>

Агабабян Ирина Рубеновна
кандидат медицинских наук, доцент,
заведующая кафедрой терапии ФПДО,
Самаркандского Государственного
медицинского института

Алиева Нигора Рустамовна
доктор медицинских наук, заведующая
кафедрой Госпитальной педиатрии №1
с основами нетрадиционной медицины
ТашПМИ

Исмаилова Адолат Абдурахимовна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор,
заведующая лабораторией
фундаментальной иммунологии
Института иммунологии геномики
человека АН РУз

Камалов Зайнитдин Сайфутдинович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор,
заведующий лабораторией
иммунорегуляции Института
иммунологии и геномики
человека АН РУз

Каюмов Улугбек Каримович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор,
заведующий кафедрой внутренних
болезней и телемедицины Центра
развития профессиональной
квалификации медицинских работников

Хусинова Шоира Акбаровна
кандидат философских наук, доцент,
заведующая кафедрой общей практики,
семейной медицины ФПДО
Самаркандского Государственного
медицинского института

Шодиколова Гуландом Зикрияевна
д.м.н., профессор, заведующая
кафедрой внутренних болезней № 3
Самаркандского Государственного
Медицинского Института
(Самарканд)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2679-1296>

Alimov Doniyor Anvarovich
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, Respublika
shoshilinch tibbiy yordam ilmiy
markazi direktori (Toshkent)

Yangiyev Baxtiyor Axmedovich
tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi,
Respublika shoshilinch tibbiy
yordam ilmiy markazining
Samarqand filiali direktori

Abdullayev Akbar Xatamovich
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, O'zbekiston
Respublikasi Sog'liqni saqlash
vazirligining "Respublika
ixtisoslashtirilgan terapiya va tibbiy
reabilitatsiya ilmiy-amaliy
tibbiyot markazi" davlat
muassasasi bosh ilmiy xodimi
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1766-4458>

Agababayan Irina Rubenovna
tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent,
DKTF, terapiya kafedrasini mudiri,
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti

Alieva Nigora Rustamovna
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, 1-sonli
gospital pediatriya kafedrasini mudiri,
ToshPTI

Ismoilova Adolat Abduraximovna
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar
akademiyasining Odam genomikasi
immunologiyasi institutining
fundamental immunologiya
laboratoriyasining mudiri

Kamalov Zaynitdin Sayfutdinovich
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar
akademiyasining Immunologiya va
inson genomikasi institutining
Immunogenetika laboratoriyasi mudiri

Qayumov Ulug'bek Karimovich
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy
malakasini oshirish markazi, ichki
kasalliklar va teletibbiyot kafedrasini
mudiri (Toshkent)

Xusinova Shoira Akbarovna
tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent,
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti
DKTF Umumiy amaliyot va oilaviy
tibbiyot kafedrasini mudiri (Samarqand)

Shodikulova Gulandom Zikriyaeвна
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti 3-
ichki kasalliklar kafedrasini mudiri
(Samarqand)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2679-1296>

Alimov Doniyor Anvarovich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Director of
the Republican Scientific Center of
Emergency Medical Care

Yangiev Bakhtiyor Axmedovich
PhD, Director of Samarkand branch of
the Republican Scientific Center of
Emergency Medical Care

Abdullaev Akbar Xatamovich
Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Chief Researcher of the State Institution
"Republican Specialized Scientific and
Practical Medical Center for Therapy and
Medical Rehabilitation" of the Ministry of
Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1766-4458>

Agababayan Irina Rubenovna
PhD, Associate Professor, Head of the
Department of Therapy, FAGE,
Samarkand State Medical Institute

Alieva Nigora Rustamovna
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the
Department of Hospital Pediatrics No. 1
with the basics of alternative medicine,
TashPMI

Ismailova Adolat Abduraximovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Laboratory of Fundamental
Immunology of the Institute of
Immunology of Human
Genomics of the Academy of Sciences
of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Kamalov Zaynitdin Sayfutdinovich
doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Laboratory of
Immunogenetics of the Institute of
Immunology and Human Genomics
of the Academy of Sciences of the
Republic of Uzbekistan

Kayumov Ulugbek Karimovich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Department of Internal
Diseases and Telemedicine of the Center
for the development of professional
qualifications
of medical workers

Khusinova Shoira Akbarovna
PhD, Associate Professor, Head of the
Department of General Practice,
Family Medicine FAGE of the
Samarkand State Medical Institute

Shodikulova Gulandom Zikriyaeвна
Doctor of Medical Sciences, professor,
head of the Department of Internal
Diseases N 3 of Samarkand state medical
institute (Samarkand)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2679-1296>

Халиков Каххор Мирзаевич
кандидат медицинских наук, доцент
заведующий кафедрой биологической
химии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского
университета

Аннаев Музаффар
Ассистент кафедры внутренних
болезней и кардиологии №2
Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
(технический секретарь)

Тулабаева Гавхар Миракбаровна
Заведующая кафедрой кардиологии,
Центр развития профессиональной
квалификации медицинских
работников, д.м.н., профессор

**Абдумаджидов Хамидулла
Амануллаевич**
Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу
Али ибн Сино. Кафедра «Хирургические
болезни и реанимация». Доктор
медицинских наук, профессор.

Саидов Максуд Арифович
к.м.н., директор Самаркандского
областного отделения
Республиканского специализированного
научно-практического медицинского
центра кардиологии (г. Самарканд)

Насирова Зарина Акбаровна
PhD, ассистент кафедры внутренних
болезней №2 Самаркандского
Государственного Медицинского
университета (ответственный
секретарь)

Xalikov Qaxxor Mirzayevich
Tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
Biologik kimyo kafedrasini mudiri

Annayev Muzaffar G'iyos o'g'li
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti 2-son
ichki kasalliklar va kardiologiya kafedrasini
assistenti (texnik kotib)

Tulabayeva Gavxar Mirakbarovna
kardiologiya kafedrasini mudiri, tibbiyot
xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini rivojlantirish
markazi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abdumadjidov Xamidulla Amanullayevich
«Abu Ali ibn Sino nomidagi Buxoro davlat
tibbiyot oliygohi» Xirurgiya kasalliklari va
reanimatsiya kafedrasini professori, tibbiyot
fanlari doktori.

Saidov Maqsud Arifovich
tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi,
Respublika ixtisoslashgan kardialogiya
ilmiy amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand
viloyat mintaqaviy filiali direktori
(Samarqand)

Nasirova Zarina Akbarovna
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti
2-sonli ichki kasalliklar kafedrasini
assistenti, PhD (mas'ul kotib)

Khalikov Kakhor Mirzayevich
Candidate of Medical Sciences,
Associate Professor, Head of the Department
of Biological Chemistry, Samarkand State
Medical University

Annaev Muzaffar
Assistant of the Department of Internal
Diseases and Cardiology No. 2 of the
Samarkand State Medical University
(technical secretary)

Tulabayeva Gavxar Mirakbarovna
Head of the Department of Cardiology,
Development Center professional
qualification of medical workers,
MD, professor

**Abdumadjidov Khamidulla
Amanullayevich**
"Bukhara state medical institute named
after Abu Ali ibn Sino". DSc, professor.

Saidov Maksud Arifovich
Candidate of Medical Sciences, Director
of the Samarkand Regional Department of
the Republican Specialized Scientific and
Practical Medical Center of Cardiology
(Samarkand)

Nasyrova Zarina Akbarovna
PhD, Assistant of the Department of Internal
Diseases No. 2 of the Samarkand State
Medical University (Executive Secretary)

ОБЗОРНЫЕ СТАТЬИ/ REVIEW ARTICLES/ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

1. **Парпиева Н.Н., Аждаблаева Д.Н.**
Возможности превентивного лечения в профилактике активных форм туберкулеза у детей с латентной туберкулезной инфекцией
Parpiyeva N.N., Adjablayeva D.N.
Possibilities of preventive treatment in prevention of active forms of tuberculosis in children with latent tuberculosis infection
Parpiyeva N.N., Adjablayeva D.N.
Latent sil infeksiyasi mavjud bo'lgan bolalarda silning faol turlarini oldini olish uchun preventiv davolashni ko'llash imkoniyatlari..... 10
2. **Турдибеков Х.И., Ким А.А., Пардаева У.Дж., Куйлиев К.У.**
Молекулярно-генетические особенности формирования бронхиальной астмы и роль полиморфизмов гена β_2 -адренорецептора
Turdibekov X.I., Kim A.A., Pardayeva U.Dj., Kuyliyev K.U.
Molecular-genetic aspects of bronchial asthma formation and the importance of β_2 -adrenoreceptor gene polymorphisms **Turdibekov X.I., Kim A.A., Pardayeva U.Dj., Kuyliyev K.U.**
Bronxial astma shakllanishining molekulyar-genetik jixatlari va bunda β_2 -adrenoreseptor geni polimorfizmlarining ahamiyati..... 14

ОРИГИНАЛЬНЫЕ СТАТЬИ/ ORIGINAL STATE/ ORIGINAL MAQOLALAR

3. **Аляви А.Л., Тошев Б.Б.**
Роль эхокардиографии при диагностике ишемической болезни сердца и мониторинга терапии триметазидином у пациентов ишемической болезнью сердца
Alyavi A. L., Toshev B. B.
The role of echocardiography in the diagnosis of coronary heart disease and monitoring of trimetazidin therapy in patients with coronary heart disease
Alyavi A. L., Toshev B. B.
Yurak ishemik kasalligini tashhislash va yurak ishemik kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarda trimetazidin terapiyasini kuzatishda exokardiografiyaning ahamiyati..... 20
4. **Атаева М.С., Ибрагимова М.Ф.**
Состояние цитокинового профиля при атипичных пневмониях у часто болеющих детей
Ataeva M.S., Ibragimova M.F.
State of the cytokine profile in atypical pneumonia in frequently ill children
Ataeva M.S., Ibragimova M.F.
Tez-tez kasal bo'lgan bolalardagi atipik pnevmoniyadagi sitokin profilining holati..... 28
5. **Закиряева П.О., Ахатова В.П.**
Благоприятное влияние снижения массы тела на дыхательную функцию у пациентов с интерстициальным заболеванием легких с ожирением
Zakiryayeva P.O., Axatova V.P.
Beneficial impact of weight loss on respiratory function in interstitial lung disease patients with obesity
Zakiryayeva P.O., Axatova V.P.
O'pka interstitial kasalligi bo'lgan ortiqcha vaznli bemorlarda vazn yo'qotishning nafas olish funksiyasiga foydali ta'siri 31
6. **Ибрагимова М.Ф., Атаева М.С., Эсанова М.Р.**
Состояние гуморального иммунитета у больных с хламидийной пневмонией у новорожденных детей
Ibragimova M.F., Ataeva M.S., Esanova M.R.
State of humoral immunity in patients with chlamydial pneumonia in newborn children
Ibragimova M.F., Ataeva M.S., Esanova M.R.
Yangi tug'ilgan bolalarda chlamidial pnevmoniya bo'lgan bemorlarda gumoral immunitet holati..... 35
7. **Исмаилов Ж.А., Расули Ф.О., Тураев Х.Н.**
Острый инфаркт миокарда как социально значимая проблема
Ismailov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Turaev H.N.
Acute myocardial infarction as a socially significant problem
Ismailov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Turaev H.N.
Miokard infarkti dolzarb ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan muammo sifatida..... 38
8. **Исмаилов Ж.А., Расули Ф.О., Тураев Х.Н.**
Эффективность своевременной госпитализации больных с острым инфарктом миокарда
Ismailov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Turaev H.N.
Efficiency of timely hospitalization of patients with acute myocardial infarction
Ismailov J.A., Rasuli F.O., Turaev H.N.
Miokard infarkti aniqlangan bemorlarni erta gospitalizatsiya qilishning samaradorligi..... 42

9	<p>Киличев А.А., Ризаев Ж.А. Динамика качества жизни больных с ишемической болезнью сердца, после аортокоронарного шунтирования Qilichev A.A., Rizaev J.A. Dynamics of quality of life in patients with coronary heart disease after aortocoronary bypass graft Qilichev A.A., Rizayev J.A. Aorta-koronar shuntlash amaliyotidan keyin yurak ishemik kasalligi bilan ogʻrigan bemorlar hayot sifati dinamikasi.....</p>	47
10	<p>Киличев А.А., Ризаев Ж.А. Улучшение качества жизни больных ишемической болезнью сердца Qilichev A.A., Rizayev J.A. Improving the quality of life of patients with coronary heart disease Qilichev A.A., Rizayev J.A. Yurak ishemik kasalligi bilan ogʻrigan bemorlarning hayot sifati yaxshilash.....</p>	52
11	<p>Маматкулова Ф.Х. Эссенциальная тромбоцитемия – основные анализы у детей и подростков Mamatkulova F.Kh. Essential thrombocythemia - basic analyzes in children and adolescents Mamatkulova F.X. Essensial trombotsitemiya- bolalar va oʻsmirlardagi asosiy tahlillar.....</p>	58
12	<p>Маматова Н.Т., Ашуров А.А., Абдухакимов А.Б. Важность теста Gene Xpert MTB/RIF в диагностике туберкулеза Mamatova N.T., Ashurov A.A., Abduhakimov A.B. The importance of the Gene Xpert MTB/RIF test in the diagnosis of tuberculosis Mamatova N.T., Ashurov A.A., Abduhakimov A.B. Tuberkulyoz diagnostikasida Gene Xpert MBT/RIF testing ahamiyati.....</p>	63
13	<p>Окбоев Т.А. Значение Ig E в раннем выявлении и прогнозировании развития заболевания в семье у лиц с наследственной предрасположенностью к семейной бронхиальной астме Okboyev T.A. The importance of Ig E in the early detection and prediction of the development of the disease in the family in persons with a hereditary predisposition to familial bronchial asthma Okboyev T. A. Oilaviy bronxial astmaga irsiy moyil boʻlgan oiladagi shaxslarda kasallik rivojlanishini erta aniqlash va bashoratlashda IG E ahamiyati.....</p>	67
14	<p>Холжигитова М.Б., Убайдуллаева Н.Н., Расули Ф. О. Клинические особенности хронической обструктивной болезни легких в зависимости от перенесенной COVID-19 Kholjigitova M.B., Ubaidullaeva N.N., Rasuli F.O. Clinical features of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease depending on the history of COVID-19 Xoljigitova M.B., Ubaidullaeva N.N., Rasuli F.O. COVID-19 oʻtkazgan surunkali obstruktiv oʻpka kasalligi boʻlgan bemorlarda klinik belgilarning oʻziga xos koʻrinishlari.....</p>	71
15	<p>Шавази Н.Н. Оценка биохимических показателей у беременных с угрозой преждевременных родов Shavazi N.N. Assessment of biochemical indicators in pregnant women with threatening preterm labor Shavazi N.N. Erta tugʻilish xavfi boʻlgan homilador ayollarda biokimyoviy koʻrsatkichlarni baholash.....</p>	77
16	<p>Шамсутдинова Г.Б., Гадаева Н.А. Влияние различных компонентов препаратов на дисфункцию эндотелия и функциональный резерв почек у пациентов с хронической сердечной недостаточностью Shamsutdinova G.B., Gadaeva N.A. Influence of drugs of various components on endothelial dysfunction and functional renal reserve in patients with chronic heart failure Shamsutdinova G.B., Gadaeva N.A. Surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligi mavjud bemorlarda turli tarkibli muolajalarining endotelial disfunktsiya va buyrak funksional zaxirasiga taʼsiri.....</p>	83
17	<p>Шодиккулова Г.З., Шагазатова Б.Х., Шоназарова Н.Х. Лечение коморбидной патологии у больных ревматоидным артритом Shodikulova G.Z., Shagazatova B.Kh., Shonazarova N.Kh. Treatment of comorbid pathology in patients with rheumatoid arthritis Shodikulova G.Z., Shagazatova B.X., Shonazarova N.X. Rевматоид артрит bilan ogʻrigan bemorlarda komorbid patologiyani davolash.....</p>	87

ISSN: 2181-0974
www.tadqiqot.uz**JOURNAL OF CARDIORESPIRATORY RESEARCH**
ЖУРНАЛ КАРДИОРЕСПИРАТОРНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна
PhD, доцент, заведующая кафедрой
акушерства и гинекологии №3
медицинского факультета
Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

ОЦЕНКА БИОХИМИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ С УГРОЗОЙ ПРЕЖДЕВРЕМЕННЫХ РОДОВ

For citation: Shavazi N.N. Assessment of biochemical indicators in pregnant women with threatening preterm labor. Journal of cardiorespiratory research. 2023, vol 4, issue 3, pp.77-82

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10052894>

АННОТАЦИЯ

Установлено, что у беременных из группы риска преждевременных родов также зарегистрированы повторная беременность, повторные роды, выкидыш, неразвивающаяся беременность в анамнезе, медикаментозный аборт, воспалительная патология репродуктивной системы и др. Однако для выявления реальных факторов риска развития ПР определяли активность важнейших компонентов системы гомеостаза, таких как наличие эндотоксикоза, активация перекисного окисления липидов, антиоксидантная защита, интенсификация цитокинов, состояние реактивных белков, организма, содержание продуктов пуринового обмена и стабильность системы гемостаза.

Ключевые слова: преждевременные роды, антиоксидантная система, синдром эндогенной интоксикации, цитокины.

Shavazi Nargiz Nuralievna

PhD, Associate professor, Head of Department
of obstetrics and gynecology №3 of medicine faculty
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

ASSESSMENT OF BIOCHEMICAL INDICATORS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH THREATING PRETERM LABOR**ANNOTATION**

It was found that re-pregnancy, re-birth, miscarriage, a history of non-developing pregnancy, medical abortion, inflammatory pathologies of the reproductive system, etc. were also registered in pregnant women at risk of preterm birth. However, in order to identify real risk factors for PR, the activities of the most important components of the homeostasis system were determined, such as the presence of endotoxemia, activation of lipid peroxidation, antioxidant protection, cytokine intensification, the state of the reactive proteins of the body, the content of the product of purine metabolism, and the stability of the hemostasis system.

Keywords: premature birth, antioxidant system, endogenous intoxication syndrome, cytokines.

Shavazi Nargiz Nuralievna

PhD, dotsent, Tibbiyot fakulteti №3
akusherlik va ginekologiya kafedrasini mudiri
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

ERTA TUG'ILISH XAVFI BO'LGAN HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA BOKIMYOVIY KO'RSATKICHLARNI BAHOLASH**ANNOTATSIIYA**

Erta tug'ilish xavfi ostida bo'lgan homilador ayollarda ham takroriy homiladorlik, qayta tug'ilish, homila tushishi, rivojlanmagan homiladorlik tarixi, tibbiy abort, reproduktiv tizimning yallig'lanish patologiyalari va boshqalar qayd etilganligi aniqlandi. Shu bilan birga, PR uchun haqiqiy xavf omillarini aniqlash uchun gomeostaz tizimining eng muhim tarkibiy qismlarining faoliyati aniqlandi, masalan, endotoksikoz mavjudligi, lipid peroksidatsiyasining faollashishi, antioksidant himoyasi, sitokinlarning kuchayishi, reaktiv oqsillarning holati. tananing, purin almashinuvi mahsulotining tarkibi va gemostaz tizimining barqarorligi.

Kalit so'zlar: erda tug'ilish, antioksidant tizim, endogen intoksikasiya sindromi, sitokinlar.

Preterm birth does not raise doubts among scientists around the world, primarily because of the significant contribution to perinatal morbidity and mortality. According to the WHO global report "Born too soon" (2012), about 15 million children are born prematurely in the world every year, 1 million under the age of 5 years die from health problems associated with prematurity [13; 14; 16;]. The stillbirth rate in untimely delivery is 8-13 times higher than in term delivery. The frequency of preterm births on Earth varies from 5 to 18% and has not been decreasing over the past 20 years [9; 10; 15].

An important aspect in solving the problem of PR and their prevention is the identification of non-specific natural reactions of the body that initiate abortion.

Endogenous intoxication syndrome (ESI) develops in all pathological conditions associated with the blockade of the body's detoxification systems [2; 3; 4]. An important pathophysiological mechanism for the development of endotoxemia is the activation of LPO processes [1]. In the literature, we did not find data on the relationship between lipid peroxidation processes in the placenta of women whose pregnancy ended in premature birth and the formation of endogenous intoxication syndrome in it.

The leading pathogenetic factor of various pathological processes in the body is the increased generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) as a result of an imbalance of pro- and antioxidant systems and the development of oxidative (oxidative) stress [7; eleven; 12;].

According to the literature, about 40% of cases of PR are caused by infectious factors [4; 5; 6]. The leading pathogenetic mechanism in such cases is the development of a nonspecific systemic inflammatory response (SIR) of the body to infectious agents. In WIR syndrome, local tissue damage in the area of pathogen inoculation causes a combination of systemic reactions. This process is associated with dysfunction of innate and acquired immunities and is manifested by a violation of the ratio of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines. Currently, the role of cytokines in the development of preterm labor is being studied very actively [7]. Thus, there is evidence that an increase in the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the contents of the cervical canal indicates a possible risk of PR [8].

One of the key stages in the development of preterm labor is oxidative stress, described in modern literature, its role is reduced to

the activation of a systemic inflammatory response, in which metabolic disorders develop in the body of a pregnant woman.

The balance of oxidative/antioxidant status is a process that begins before birth, and premature babies are particularly susceptible to oxidative stress. The combination of hyperoxia, which enhances the production of reactive oxygen species, and low levels of antioxidants causes oxidative stress, inflammation, and even apoptosis, thereby increasing mortality and morbidity. Consistent with the mechanisms of oxidative stress and the lack of research in this area, in this prospective study we aimed to compare serum levels of prooxidant-antioxidant balance in preterm pregnant women.

The aim of our study was, development of a predictive model for the likelihood of preterm birth based on the study of anamnestic risk factors and the results of a comprehensive clinical, laboratory and instrumental study.

Materials and methods of research: to determine one of the causes of the links in the pathogenesis of PR, we observed 317 pregnant women with threatening PR at a gestational age of 22-34 weeks. Patients were included in the study as they applied and were hospitalized in the department of pathology of pregnant women in the Regional Perinatal Center of Samarkand for the period 2020-2023.

As a result of a prospective study, data such as baseline clinical characteristics, features of the course of pregnancy, as well as its outcomes in 317 pregnant women with threatening and PR were analyzed.

Patients were included in the study as they were referred. According to the data of both clinical, laboratory and functional examination methods, as well as the diagnosis, as well as in accordance with the developed criteria for inclusion in the study, all pregnant women were divided into 3 groups.

The first group (I, n=120) - pregnant women at high risk, with the threat of abortion.

The second group (II, n=157) - high-risk pregnant women who gave birth prematurely and in a timely manner.

The third group - (control, n=40) - examined 40 pregnant women with a physiological course of pregnancy and childbirth, delivered on time. (fig.1)

Figure 1. Group distribution design.

All patients included in the study underwent a standard set of examinations in accordance with the order of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 11, 2019 No. ZRU-528 “On the protection of the reproductive health of citizens”.

The age of women ranged from 19 to 38 years. The youngest age at the onset of preterm birth is 18 years, and later - at 38 years, in averaging 27+2.9 in all groups. (fig.2)

Age of the examined women

Figure 2. Distribution of surveyed women by age

In the analysis of the social position, city dwellers prevailed. According to the social status among the surveyed were: students - 18.2%, working -40.3%, housewives -41.5%.

When studying the parity, the highest frequency of multi-pregnant women was observed in the second group, primigravidas - in the first. In group 3, both primigravidas and recurrent pregnancies occurred with approximately equal frequency. Primiparous - to a greater extent noted in the second, multiparous - in the first.

The frequency of induced labor was 21 (17.5%) of the first group and 77 (49%) of the second, and spontaneous - 99 (82.5%) and 80 (51%) (Table 1).

According to the anamnesis, it was revealed that the number of primigravidas and re-pregnant women in the first group were 78 (65.0%) and 42 (35.0%), and the second - 62 (39.4%) and 95 (60.5%). Primiparous and multiparous were 89 (74.1%) and 31 (25.8%) women of the first group and 70 (44.5%) and 87 (55.4%) of the second.

Obstetric and gynecological history showed that miscarriage was 74 (61.1%) and 43 (27.3%), respectively. Non-developing pregnancies - 32 (26.6%) and 25 (15.9%), Hypertension - 51 (42.5%) and 69 (43.9%), and Medical abortion - 30 (25.0%) and 33 (21.0%) respectively.

It is important to note that inflammatory diseases such as salpingoophoritis, endometritis, endomyometritis, etc., of the pelvic organs were recorded in 57 (47.5%) women of the first group and 41 (26.1%) in the second (Table 1).

Thus, it was noted that high risk factors threats of termination of pregnancy and premature birth are primigravida, first childbirth, miscarriage, various kinds of abortions (spontaneous, medical), HPPT. They can negatively blame the course of pregnancy.

One of the most important issues that concerns obstetricians around the world is the optimal tactics of delivery in PR. Taking into account that at present there is no single concept of conducting PR.

Figure 3. Indicators of birth outcomes of the study group.

UD – urgent delivery
PB – premature birth
CS – cesarian section

According to the results of analyzes of timely and PR, it was revealed that among all the studied groups (n=317), childbirth ended more often through the natural birth canal (Fig. 3).

According to the analysis of the outcome of childbirth in the prospective group, in group I, SR was 74.1% (89) of cases, and PR was

25.9% (31), in the second group, SR was 37.5% (59), and PR was 62, 5% (98) of cases.

In recent years, the systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) and oxidative stress have played an important role in the pathogenesis of PR development. The development of oxidative stress

is due to an imbalance between the generation and elimination of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Our research results, presented in the table, showed that the content of lipid peroxidation products in the blood plasma of pregnant women in the control group was 41.54±3.67 μmol/l. It was noted that with the progression of the disease, the content of TBA-active products significantly increases, 78.14±6.89 μmol/l in pregnant women of group II versus 41.54±3.67 μmol/l in healthy pregnant women (p<0.05).

Simultaneously with the activation of oxidative processes, there is an increase in the activity of blood catalase in pregnant women of group I up to 13.57±1.56 cat/l, group II up to values of -11.32±1.27 cat/l,

against 7.98±0,81cat/l to the control group, which indicates an increase in the antioxidant activity of the blood. An increase in the activity of blood catalase in patients of group II indicates the depletion of the antioxidant defense system, which is indirectly confirmed by the activity of SOD and the content of TBA-active products in this group, compared with the control. There is a decrease in SOD activity in group I by 45%, in group II by 64% compared with healthy pregnant women. There are also suggestions that it is the consequences of decompensation of antioxidant protection that contribute to the accumulation of LPO products.

Table 1.

Table 1. Analysis of LPO-AOS indicators in pregnant women with premature childbirth

Indicators	I group (n=41)	II group (n=42)	III-group (n=35)
TBA-active products, μmol/l	67.23±5.78	78.14±6.89*	41.54±3.67
Catalase activity cat/l	13.57±1.56*	11.32±1.27*	7.98±0.81
SOD activity IU/1 mg of protein	3.46±0.29*	2.31±0.21*	6.34±0.58

Note: * - the difference is significant when compared with the control group, p<0.05;

The physiological course of pregnancy is accompanied by a certain restructuring of the immune system, which ensures the tolerance of the mother's body to the antigens of the fetal egg and gestation. It has now become apparent that the defense of the fetus against a damaging maternal immune response is based on a complex mechanism and that communication between different steps in the cascade of events is mediated by cytokines.

It has been established that during the normal course of pregnancy, the cytokine status shifts towards immunosuppressive cytokines (IL-4, IL-10, TGF-β), which inhibit cellular immunity reactions and stimulate the production of blocking antibodies. In our study, the level of anti-inflammatory cytokines IL-4 and IL-10, respectively, was significantly lower by 1.6 and 2.5 times than in the control group. In this situation, the most informative indicators were IL-10, low values of which can serve as a marker of the risk of developing PR.

Table 2.

Table 2. Indicators of cytokine status in pregnant women with threatened preterm labor

Index	I group (n=41)	II group (n=42)	III-group (n=35)
IL-1 c, pg/ml	3.31± 0.27*	4.35±0.38 *	2.15±0.18
IL-2, pg/ml	9.53±0.84	7.54± 0.64*	11.14±0.91
IL-4, pg/ml	2.24± 0.17*	2.15± 0.13*	3.58±0.19
IL-6, pg/ml	3.78±0.35*	4.83±0.39*	2.38±0.19
IL-8, pg/ml	8.51± 0.79*	10.98± 1.03*	5.42±0.51
IL-10, pg/ml	9.01±0.82*	7.36±0.62*	22.48±1.96
TNF-a, pg/ml	2.68± 0.27*	3.14± 0.23*	1.76±0.14

Note: * - the difference is significant when compared with the control group, p<0.05;

Therefore, in pregnant women at risk of preterm birth, significant disturbances occur in the cytokine system, which may be accompanied by the penetration of pro-inflammatory cytokines into the systemic circulation, which, in our opinion, contributes to the pathogenesis of PR. In addition, an increase in TNF-α and cytokines can serve as markers of inflammation of the endothelium of the uterine vessels, and also indicate a high permeability of the membranes of the membranes, which, in our opinion, is one of the reasons for the mechanisms of preterm labor and amniotic fluid rupture.

Particular attention is given to pregnant women at high risk of PR, in which the level of ceruloplasmin was lower than the control group.

As the results of the study showed, in the first group the level of ceruloplasmin was 12.6 g/l, in the second group it was reduced to 10.4

g/l in the control group 20.2 g/l.

In a comparative analysis of the level of another protein S100 in the serum of pregnant women, a tendency to its decrease was noted in groups I and II compared with patients in the CG. The average content of S100B protein in the blood serum of women in the control group was 60.9±5.08 mc/ml, while in the first group bql was reduced to 32.80±13.41 mc/ml, in the second group 33.90±10.21 μ/ml (>0.05). In women who experienced PR after a threat of miscarriage in the period from 22 to 34 weeks, a decrease in the level of S100B protein was found compared to pregnant women in the control group (33.48±7.3 and 60.9±5.08 mc/ml, <0.01).

Table 3.

Table 3. The content of S-100 protein in women of the studied groups

Index	I group (n=41)	II group (n=42)	III-group (n=35)
S-100 protein	32.80±13.41	33.90±10.21	60.9±5.08

Note: *-significance of differences P <0.05

Serum content of S100B, equal to or less than 43.66 µg/ml, is also a new prognostic criterion for AR and increases the risk of their onset after a threatened abortion at 22–34 weeks by 3.15 times.

When studying the analysis of hemostasis, it was demonstrated that preterm labor is characterized by changes in coagulation and fibrinolytic activity in the form of hypercoagulability and hypofibrinolysis.

In women of the main group, a shortening of the APTT time and

PT by 33.3% and 31.2% ($p < 0.05$) relative to the control group was noted.

In high-risk pregnant women who gave birth prematurely, APTT and PT were lower than the control group by 20.1 and 25.4% ($p < 0.05$).

In the group where pregnant women at high risk of PR who gave birth in a timely manner, the time of APTT and PT was reduced by 15.6 and 17.1% ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Study of the hemostasis system in the studied groups

APTT - activated partial thromboplastin time

PT – Prothrombin time

When studying the process of fibrinolysis in PR, it was found that the amount of fibrinogen was exceeded in the main group by 51.8, 39.4 and ($p < 0.05$) when compared with the control group

So, the development of preterm labor is accompanied by the formation of endogenous intoxication in pregnant women. With a high risk of PR and the threat of interruption, the intensity of toxemia was recorded to the greatest extent relative to other women who gave birth prematurely and in a timely manner.

Thus, one of the pathogenetic factors of PR is the activation of the processes of free-radical destabilization of biological membranes, accompanied by an excessive increase in the content of peroxide compounds in the blood, as well as malondialdehyde, diene conjugates and catalase with a pronounced universal cytopathogenic effect and a decrease in the amount of SOD.

Thus, our results of the study allow us to state that the study of the cytokine balance is significant for assessing the direction of the immune response, as well as the outcome of pregnancy for the mother and fetus.

Therefore, the results of our studies indicate that the study of the dependence of endothelial dysfunction on the profile of factors affecting the endothelium is a promising direction in the development of methods for the prevention and treatment of preterm birth.

Summing up the results of these study groups, it was found that re-pregnancy, re-birth, miscarriage, a history of non-developing pregnancy, medical abortion, inflammatory pathologies of the reproductive system, etc. were also recorded in pregnant women at risk of preterm birth. However, in order to identify real risk factors for PR, the activities of the most important components of the homeostasis system were determined, such as the presence of endotoxemia, activation of lipid peroxidation, antioxidant protection, cytokine intensification, the state of the reactive proteins of the body, the content of the product of purine metabolism, and the stability of the hemostasis system.

Список литературы / References / Iqriboslar

1. B. H. Al Wattar, J. A. Tamblyn, W. Parry-Smith, et al., Management of obstetric postpartum haemorrhage: a national service assessment of current practice in the UK. *Risk Manag Healthc Policy*, 10, 1-6 (2017)
2. Conde-Agudelo A, Romero R. Does vaginal progesterone prevent recurrent preterm birth in women with a singleton gestation and a history of spontaneous preterm birth? Evidence from a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2022 Sep;227(3):440-461.e2. doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2022.04.023. Epub 2022 Apr 20. PMID: 35460628; PMCID: PMC9420758.
3. Kim JI Multiple factors in the second trimester of pregnancy on preterm labor symptoms and preterm birth / JI Kim, MO Cho, GY Choi // *J. Korean. Acad. Nurs.* - 2017. - Vol. 47, No. 3. - P. 357-366.
4. L. S. Abdullaeva, On the issue of prevention of obstetric bleeding in the syndrome of an overgrown uterus, *Yangi uzbekistonda milliy tarakkiyot va innovatsiyalar*, 338-342 (2022)
5. Liu, Y. Early- or mid-trimester amniocentesis biomarkers for predicting preterm delivery: a meta-analysis / Y. Liu, Y. Liu, R. Zhang [et al.] // *Ann Med.* - 2017. - Vol. 49, No. 1. - P. 1-10.
6. N. A. Akhtamova, N. N. Shavazi, Prediction of obstetric blood loss in women with preterm birth (literature review), *Uzbek medical journal*, 3(5) (2022)

7. N. N. Shavazi, et al., Total gisterektomiyaning subtotal gisterektomiyadan ustunvorligini tahlillash, *Journal of biomedicine and practice*, **7(3)** (2022)
8. N. N. Shavazi, P. B. Alimova, Modern aspects of obstetric bleeding (review of literature), *Journal of reproductive health and damage-nephrological research*, **3(2)** (2022)
9. N. N. Shavazi, Z. B. Babamuradova, The ratio of pro- and antiangiogenic factors in the pathogenesis of preterm labor in pregnant women against the background of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, *European Research: innovation in science, education and technology*, 93-96 (2020)
10. O. F. Akhtamova, Antiphospholipid syndrome and a mistruction, *Uzbek medical journal*, 3(4) (2022)
11. R. Anderson, S. Daher, L. Regan, M. Al-Memar, T. Born, D. A. McIntyre, R. Rai, O. B. Christiansen, M. Sugiura-Ogasawara, J. Odendal, A. J. Devall, P. R. Bennett, S. Petru, A. Coomarasami, Issues of miscarriage: the epidemiological, physical, psychological, and economic costs of early pregnancy loss., *Lancet*. May 1, **397(10285)**, 1658-1667 (2021)
12. S. A. Tilyavova, Modern approaches to the diagnostics and treatment of urinary disorders in premenopause women, *Uzbek medical journal*, 3(3) (2022)
13. S. N. Nuraliyevna, J. M. Dilshodovna, Morphofunctional structure of the placenta in premature labor, *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 381-384 (2022)
14. Walani SR. Global burden of preterm birth. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2020 Jul;150(1):31-33. doi: 10.1002/ijgo.13195. PMID: 32524596.
15. Negmatovna, T. E., Khudayberdievich, Z. S., Sayfutdinovich, K. Z., Khidirnazarovich, T. D., Shukhratovna, K. F., & Abdullaevna, A. G. (2019). Urate regulation gene polymorphisms are correlated with clinical forms of coronary heart disease. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 11(3), 198-202.
16. Махкамова Н. У. Эффективность комплексной терапии хронических цереброваскулярных расстройств у пациентов с артериальной гипертензией //Український хіміотерапевтичний журнал. – 2013. – №. 3-4. – С. 63-65.
17. Махкамова Н. У., Ходжаев А. И. Частота встречаемости и структура цереброваскулярных осложнений артериальной гипертензии у лиц узбекской национальности с различными полиморфизмами генов ангиотензинпревращающего фермента и аполипопротеина Е //Евразийский кардиологический журнал. – 2012. – №. 2. – С. 55-58.

ЖУРНАЛ КАРДИОРЕСПИРАТОРНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF CARDIORESPIRATORY RESEARCH

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 3

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000